

**EVALUATION OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL SCIENCES
EDUCATIONAL STUDY****Adinda Putri Dewanny¹, Ahmad Djuman Kurniawan², Basar Ihsan³, Faisal Alkatsiri⁴,
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Article History: Submitted: 2023.05.28 Revised: 2023.05.29 Accepted: 2022.06.07 Published: 2023.06.30

ABSTRACT

This research aims to evaluate the development of Social Sciences education studies using methods Systematic Literature Review (SLR). This research was carried out by searching and reviewing related library sources and references. Based on this research, it can be concluded that social studies learning in general has not run optimally. Evaluations or improvements need to be carried out by school principals, teachers and the government to support history learning programs that are integrated in social studies. Learning evaluation is very important so that a teacher can find out the extent of students' progress. Because knowledge about student progress also has various uses and improvements to the learning system. As we know, learning is a system that has various components such as objectives, materials, methods, media and learning resources, environment, teachers and students. Social studies learning itself is expected to be able to make a good impression in the hearts of students. So that it makes students social creatures who can socialize or interact well in society. More than that, students are expected to be able to become individuals who know their environment, know that the world is wide, know the diversity in the world, know how to interact well in society, and how they will be useful in society in the future. It also allows students to access material easily, anywhere and at any time, not just limited to material presented by teachers when studying at school.

Keywords: Development Evaluation, Learning, Social Sciences education**INTRODUCTION**

Learning is the process of student interaction with educators and learning resources in a learning environment. Learning is the help provided by educators so that the process of acquiring knowledge and knowledge, mastery of skills and habits, as well as the formation of attitudes and trust in students can occur. In other words, learning is a process to help students learn well. Learning is a process carried out by teachers in guiding, helping and directing students to have learning experiences. Learning is concerned with the activities of how teachers teach and how students learn.

Gagne in Sanjaya (2012: 100) said that learning is designing and arranging various resources and facilities that are available for students to use or utilize in learning something. Learning consists of two aspects that collaborate with each other, namely learning focused on student activities and teaching oriented towards what the teacher must do. (Asep Jihad and Abdul Haris, 2008:11). Thus, learning can be interpreted as an effort to regulate conditions that allow interaction between students and learning resources to achieve set goals.

An effective learning process is characterized by achieving goals. Therefore, before the learning process begins, teachers need to formulate learning objectives, namely general learning objectives and specific learning objectives. General learning objectives are general objectives that involve various subjects, while specific learning objectives are an elaboration of general learning objectives which are realized in the form of lesson units.

Mager formulated the concept of learning objectives to focus on student behavior or actions as output for students, which can be observed. Thus, the learning process has a certain impact on student behavior. S. Bloom details learning objectives including cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects. In this case it leads to cognitive which has six levels, namely: Knowledge (knowledge) examples of goals related to the ability to remember, memorize, repeat, and imitate, Comprehension (understanding) examples of goals related to the goal of understanding. Restate other forms and interpret, Application (application) examples of goals related to the application of theories, principles and information, Analysis (analysis), this goal is related to problem analysis, Synthesis (synthesis), an example of a goal related to combining parts in a container, Evaluation (evaluation), an example of a goal related to determining certain criteria for an activity.

Quality learning really depends on student motivation and teacher creativity. Learners who have high motivation are supported by teachers who are able to facilitate this motivation, which will lead to successful achievement of learning targets. Learning targets can be measured through changes in students' attitudes and abilities through the learning process. Good learning design, supported by good facilities, coupled with teacher creativity will make it easier for students to achieve learning targets.

Social Science Learning is an educational program and not a separate sub-discipline, so it will not be found either in the nomenclature of philosophy of science, social science disciplines (social science), as well as educational sciences. (Rudi Gunawan, 2012:17). IPS is an integration of various branches of social sciences, such as sociology, history, geography, economics, politics, law and culture. The study of Social Sciences learning material includes human life in society or humans as members of society based on geographic, economic, sociological and historical dimensions. (Trianto, 2015:171).

Social Sciences are formulated on the basis of reality and social phenomena in society which are realized in an interdisciplinary approach from aspects and branches of social science. Social studies or social studies is part of the school curriculum which is derived from the material content of the branches of social sciences, namely sociology, history, geography, economics, politics, anthropology, philosophy and social psychology. (Trianto, 2010: 171)

According to Djodjo Suradisastra et al (1991: 4) say that: "basically social studies is the study of humans and the world around them". This means that the main subject of study in social studies lessons is the relationship between humans and the environment in people's real lives.

The development of social studies education continues to experience changes in both learning materials and activities according to the conditions of students and their environment. Where today's student environment has been influenced by technological developments in its time. The current generation of students is generation Z, where children wake up and immediately see smartphone or tablet both of whom were connected to the internet, it turned out that many messages came in from various media that they followed and came in while they were sleeping (Huriah Rachmah, 2014: 246). This shows that the current condition of students is students who cannot be separated from smartphone. They feel they are dependent on smartphone, because with smartphone You don't need to go anywhere but you can see the wide world.

IPS is formulated on the basis of reality and social phenomena which embodies an interdisciplinary approach from aspects and branches of social sciences (sociology, history, geography, economics, politics, law and culture). The content of the material contained in the social studies content is very broad and is always evolving with the times. Therefore, there is a need for an evaluation of productive social studies learning output or enable students to socialize well in society. That social studies learning is deeper than the material that has been provided. Social studies learning is not just material related to Sociology, Economics, Geography, or History or an integration of the four.

More than that, students are expected to be able to become individuals who know their environment, know that the world is wide, know the diversity in the world, know how to interact well in society, and how they will be useful in society in the future. It also allows students to access material easily, anywhere and at any time, not just limited to material presented by teachers when studying at school.

The word evaluation itself comes from English evaluation, in Indonesian means assessment. In this way, it is a literal evaluation of education (education evaluation) can be interpreted as an assessment in the field of education or an assessment of matters relating to educational activities (Sudijono, 2001).

Educational evaluation is a process of collecting data to determine the extent, in what terms, and in what part of the educational objectives has been achieved. If not yet, how is it not yet and what is the reason". A broader definition was presented by two other experts, namely Crobach and Stufflebeam.

Theoretically, learning evaluation is very important so that a teacher can find out the extent of students' progress. Because knowledge about student progress also has various uses and improvements to the learning system. As we know, learning is a system that has various components such as objectives, materials, methods, media and learning resources, environment, teachers and students.

Edward A. Suchman, professor of sociology at the University of Pittsburgh wrote a book entitled *evaluative Research : Prinsiples and practice in public servis an social action program* (1987) which shows his views on evaluation as a form of research. He distinguishes between evaluation as a use of public opinion (common sense) which shows a social process. make an assessment of the benefits (worth) dan evaluation research (evaluative research) which uses scientific research methods and techniques. He uses word *evaluative* as an adjective specifying a type of research. He stated the importance of carrying out evaluative research using scientific methods. Stufflebean and Srinkfield (2007) suggest that Suchman supports Bigman's opinion that the purpose of evaluation is to: discover whether and how well program objectives are met, determine the reasons for the success or failure of a program, muncover the principles that make a program successful, directing the process of experimenting with techniques to increase its effectiveness.

In general, the purpose of learning evaluation is to determine the effectiveness of the learning process that has been implemented. Indicators of effectiveness can be seen from changes in behavior that occur in students. Ministry of National Education (2003: 6) stated that the objectives of learning evaluation are to:

- a. Seeing the productivity and effectiveness of teaching and learning activities
- b. Improving and perfecting educators' activities.
- c. Improve, perfect and develop teaching and learning programs.
- d. Knowing what difficulties students face during learning activities and finding solutions.
- e. Placing students in appropriate teaching and learning situations according to their abilities.

A creative teacher means being able to utilize the surrounding environment to support the learning process. Teacher creativity is important if teachers want to manage social studies learning in the classroom so that it is enjoyable. Teacher creativity can be targeted at social studies learning design which includes: determining KI and KD, determining lesson material, choosing learning strategies, choosing learning media, developing procedures and evaluation instruments (Gafur, 2019). Apart from that, the development of updated learning models involving information technology can also be used by social studies teachers in managing the learning process both in the classroom and outside the classroom.

The learning model itself is a prescription of teaching strategies prepared to achieve specific goals in learning (Wahab, 2017:57). This can be done by teachers, especially IPS teachers by making use of the existing environmental conditions, of course also supported by continuing to add references by finding new information in IPS learning. Conditions like this should be captured by IPS teachers to be utilized in managing the learning process. IPS teachers can modify the learning process by making use of the content available on smartphone or tablet students so that social studies learning becomes enjoyable, both at home and at school. In line with the journal *History Education* Vol. 7 No. 2 July 2018 which states that the teacher's role in this case is very important in the history learning process. Because apart from being tasked with delivering learning material, we are also obliged to foster social values in students so that they become individuals with character. Historical material in social studies education not only talks about learning about the life of a society in the past, but in it teachers can convey noble values that have existed since ancient times, which can still be related and used today.

Not only in history learning, but also in other learning which is included in the Social Sciences sub-teaching. Such as Sociology, Economics and Geography or what we usually call integrated social studies. All four must be integrated and produce students who have a social spirit, interact well in the surrounding community.

Thus, by using models, methods, strategies and other learning tools, it is hoped that students can apply the knowledge they already have in society. So that social studies learning is not just a subject about humans and their surroundings, but also learning that has the impression and message that we are social creatures who live side by side with other humans.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses descriptive qualitative methods, with research data taken by Systematic Literature Review (SLR). Systematic Literature Review (SLR) is a term for identifying, evaluating and interpreting all available research that is relevant to the problem formulation or topic area being studied. (Calderon and

Ruiz 2015).

Systematic Literature Review (SLR) is defined as the process of identifying, assessing and interpreting all available research evidence with the aim of providing answers to specific research questions (Kitchenham, et al., 2009). SLR research is carried out to identify, evaluate, and interpret all relevant research results related to certain research questions, certain topics, or phenomena of concern (Kitchenham, 2004). The purpose of SLR research or Systematic Literature Review This is to find strategies that will help overcome the problems faced as well as identify different perspectives related to the problem being researched and reveal theories that are relevant to the case in this research which examines more deeply the influence of the benefits of information technology on the performance of teaching staff.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on research that has been carried out using research methods Systematic Literature Review (SLR). and the environment. Where today's student environment has been influenced by technological developments in its time. There was an opinion from one of the teachers at the school who said that to improve the quality of learning, social studies subjects should be separated into history, geography and economics so that teachers who have the historical discipline can concentrate on just history material as well as geography and economics. In integrating social studies subjects in the field, social studies teachers say that they adapt to the material to be studied. In terms of a conducive school environment, the school has made various efforts to create an academic atmosphere and learning environment aimed at motivating students and providing a positive influence in improving their learning outcomes, including comfortable and orderly classrooms, lots of pictures of figures, heroes on the classroom walls, a clean environment, learning facilities and infrastructure, learning resources and learning media, creating relationships between students and their friends and students with their teachers. This means that the relationship between teachers and students is very important for smooth learning in the classroom. Teachers who are able to carry out their roles well and build good relationships with students will have a positive impact on learning outcomes in the classroom.

Several social studies teachers also said that the students were very enthusiastic. Moreover, when studying outside with museum learning resources, students are very happy. But because the time is very short, we as teachers sometimes only explain briefly even though there is a lot of material that they need to know. In contrast to the opinion of students who say that the social studies learning process in class, especially history material, is very boring and uninteresting. When the social studies teacher entered the class he didn't explain to us, he just told us to take notes and give assignments.

Based on the description above, it can be seen that the integrated history learning in social studies in class VII Ambon City Junior High School is not yet optimal. Improvements need to be made by school principals, teachers and the government to support integrated history learning programs in social studies. These improvements are divided into several aspects such as curriculum aspects, facilities and infrastructure aspects, technology and information aspects so that teachers can make social studies learning memorable and implemented by students in society. Basically, social studies teachings are about human life which includes all of their behavior and needs. IPS refers to society's efforts to fulfill primary, secondary and tertiary needs, which include material and spiritual needs. These needs are related to culture, economics, living and nonliving natural resources, law and politics etc. for the survival of humanity. The social sciences also deal with interactions between people and members of society in small and large groups. These groups start from the family level as the smallest community unit, then RT/RW, Village, Village, District, Province, Parish/Regency, Province, Country and World.

The definition of social science refers to human life as social creatures. In surviving and fulfilling their needs, humans cannot be separated from interactions with other people and interactions with nature. All these functions are regulated in the social sciences. Basically, social

science is a science that regulates human activities according to their principles and characteristics. Science education is basically a mixture of various branches of social sciences and other appropriate scientific disciplines. This combination is then combined into one unit and taught in educational programs at various levels, including elementary school. The aim of this degree is to provide students with knowledge about various human social activities so that in the future students can carry out activities in interaction with other people and nature to improve human civilization in the future. To achieve this goal, a teacher must be able to develop social studies learning that is transmitted at the educational unit level. Social sciences as subjects in educational programs and not only as a sub-discipline of the sciences.

Teachers as owners of an important role in learning development activities must have a creative and innovative nature, both in the learning process and the process of evaluating the learning carried out. Learning evaluation is carried out so that teachers can find out the abilities that students have in participating in the learning process. The achievement of the material that has been presented, the skills possessed, and the attitudes of the students will be assessed through the learning evaluation process. Learning evaluation tools that will later be used by teachers in assessing students' abilities must also be accountable.

Evaluation can encourage students to be more active in studying continuously and also encourage teachers to further improve the quality of the learning process and encourage education managers to further improve the facilities and quality of student learning. In this regard, optimizing the evaluation system has two meanings, the first is evaluation system that provides optimal information. Second is the benefits achieved from evaluation. The main benefit of evaluation is improving the quality of learning. This shows that the success of the learning program is always seen from aspect learning outcomes achieved. On the other hand, evaluation of learning programs need data about implementation learning and level of achievement of learning objectives. Such conditions do not only occur at the higher education level, but also happens at levels primary and secondary education. The success of a learning program is always seen from the aspect of learning outcomes, while the implementation of the learning program in the classroom or the quality of the learning process that takes place is rarely touched by assessment activities.

Thus, evaluation is very much needed in various activities of daily human life, because whether we realize it or not, evaluations are actually often carried out, both for ourselves and other social activities. This can be seen starting from dress up, after get dressed it stand in front mirror whether his appearance is natural or not, it comes down to bigger things in human life. Likewise, in the world of education it cannot be separated from the evaluation activity itself. It is said that, because evaluation is one of the basic components of the education system which must be carried out systematically and planned as a tool to measure success or targets to be achieved in the learning process.

Learning evaluation is the process of obtaining data and information needed to determine the extent and how learning has progressed in order to make an assessment (judgment). and improvements needed to maximize the result. Learning evaluation is very important so that a teacher can find out the level of progress of students, especially in socializing in society. Because knowledge about student progress also has various useful values as well as improving the learning system. As we know, learning is a system that has various components such as objectives, materials, methods, media and learning resources, environment, teachers and students.

After analyzing several aspects, the current implementation of social studies learning needs changes in it. Regarding related aspects, there are still several shortcomings that need to be addressed in these aspects. In reality, currently social studies teachers still don't really understand integration in social studies because they are basic History, geography and economics teachers are more comfortable providing learning separately rather than in an integrated manner. Thus, it can be concluded that the development of social studies learning still has several shortcomings that need to be addressed. For example, integrated social studies learning can be carried out jointly by

several teachers, this is adjusted to each teacher's situation and school policies.

Regarding aspects related to the academic learning environment which is part of the program context, it can be seen that there are still several deficiencies that need to be addressed in these aspects. Furthermore, regarding the social studies learning program policy, in reality social studies teachers in the city of Ambon still do not understand integration in social studies because those who are basically history, geography and economics teachers are more comfortable and fluent in teaching history, geography and economics separately, not in an integrated manner. Thus, it can be concluded that there are still deficiencies that need to be addressed in this aspect. For example, integrated social studies learning can be carried out jointly by several teachers, this is adjusted to each teacher's situation and school policies.

Education in the history of human civilization is one of the most urgent components of life. Since humans have interacted with educational activities, humans have succeeded in realizing various developments and progress in all aspects of their lives. In fact, education is something natural in the development of human civilization. In parallel, the educational process is also experiencing very rapid progress, both in the form of methods, facilities and targets to be achieved. Because this is one of the characteristics and features of education, namely that it is always progressive. If education does not experience and does not cause progress or even causes setbacks, then it is not called education. Because education is an integral activity that includes targets, methods and means in forming humans who are able to interact and adapt to their environment, both internal and external in order to realize better progress.

From the aspect of the quality of the implementation of the social studies learning process that they carry out in class, namely in historical material that is integrated with social studies, it is a matter of time. The history material in the Social Sciences package book is at the end of the material after the Geography and Economics material. So the implementation of learning history material is sometimes not completed according to their learning tools because it collides with preparations for exams for class IX students and also impromptu programs from schools so that the learning process on history material is ineffective. From the perspective of the students themselves, when the students are not ready to receive lessons, they will certainly not understand the material presented by the teacher.

The methods and media used also have a large role in learning activities. Abilities that students are expected to have. Will be determined by the relevance of using a method that is appropriate to the objectives. This means that learning objectives can be achieved by using appropriate methods, according to the strategies/methods that can be used in learning activities that do not last long because they are damaged. Advances in science and technology require the use of media to be optimized.

The teaching and learning process that an educator must carry out. Teaching and learning activities cannot be separated from the close relationship between teachers, students, curriculum, facilities and infrastructure, however, in the educational process there will always be a problem that results in obstruction of the teaching and learning process. In the process of teaching and learning activities, teachers should pay more attention to the differences that exist in students so that it is easy for teachers to determine the strategies that will be used in the learning process.

Social studies learning can be designed with the theme of the discourse to be taught that can be linked to various other social science disciplines so that it is easy for students to understand. Teaching social studies, a teacher must be able to relate a concept to be taught with other social science disciplines, this of course has various problems faced by teachers, especially for teachers who usually only teach one field of study.

Social studies subjects basically aim to prepare students as good citizens (good citizenship). as good citizens, students must master knowledge (knowledge), skills (skills), attitudes and values (attitude and values) that can be used to solve personal and social problems and can make decisions to participate in community activities at the local level , regional and global. Social studies subjects cannot be separated from teaching and learning activities where a teacher in

teaching social studies is required to be more creative in delivering learning material so that the lesson material delivered by the teacher is easy for students to understand so that learning is more meaningful. A teacher's delivery of learning material must also be able to relate learning material to students' daily lives and relate it to social problems so that students are more sensitive to social problems occurring around them.

In the curriculum aspect, it can be seen that social studies teachers are having a little difficulty with changes to the curriculum, they still need time to be able to fully implement them. However, even though these curriculum changes are not yet completely effective, at least the efforts that have been made show that there is positive progress.

The development of the Social Sciences curriculum in Indonesia in terms of objective components and teaching materials continues to develop. Learning objectives essentially support national education objectives through institutional, curricular and instructional objectives. The aim of the social studies learning curriculum essentially has the same essence, namely to develop students' knowledge, understanding and analytical skills regarding the social conditions of society.

In the aspect of facilities and infrastructure as input for the social studies learning program, the facilities and infrastructure will facilitate the implementation of learning activities. Learning facilities and infrastructure include learning media and learning resources. Optimal use of learning media can improve the quality of learning.

Learning activities are not just about conveying lesson material. The learning process should change the perspective and understanding of each student and also be able to have empathy regarding past struggles. Each subject has an impact target to be achieved, social studies contains one goal so that students have the ability to commit and be aware of social and human values. Thus, after learning social studies, students should leave behind feelings that bind students about this incident, so that it creates a deeper interest in wanting to explore it.

Social studies subject matter with a historical theme requires methods that bring students' emotions to sympathy, empathy and happiness. Generating student participation is very difficult if you apply the one-way lecture method. For this reason, it is necessary to use discussion and role playing methods that make students happy and understand the meaning of struggles from various regions with the help of cameras and audio-visual media. This is very easy for students to understand, and attracts students' desire to learn even more. Using technology in teaching and learning activities can stimulate students' interest in wanting to learn in contemporary ways.

The increasingly rapid development of information technology in the current era of globalization cannot avoid its influence on the world of education. Global demands require the world of education to always and always adapt technological developments to efforts to improve the quality of education, especially adapting its use to the world of education, especially in the learning process. Information technology is the development of information systems by combining computer technology with telecommunications

The role of technology and information in social studies learning is very important. Technology and information have several benefits in social studies learning, namely as a supplement, complement and substitute. Additional roles (supplements) are said to be additional, if students have the freedom to choose. The use and use of technology as a social studies learning medium has been widely applied in the world of education. The most important thing is that all the aspects mentioned above can make social studies learning memorable and make students social creatures who are capable in society and can make sense of the life they lead.

CONCLUSION

Based on the description that has been carried out by researchers regarding "Evaluation of the Development of Social Science Education Studies" with theories related to learning evaluation and methods Systematic Literature Review (SLR) we can conclude that currently the development of studies in Social Sciences learning is slowly starting to keep up with the times and the technology used. This is good progress which certainly influences the learning process of the students themselves. Development in the

study of Social Sciences Education occurs in every aspect of learning. Such as the learning methods applied, the learning media used, the learning strategies formulated, and the infrastructure that keeps up with the times.

However, social studies learning is less impressive because most teachers only deliver the material without providing the real purpose and objectives of the material presented. There are many values contained in every material in social studies learning, especially the value of socializing and socializing properly and correctly in the surrounding environment. With this research, it is hoped that all educational institutions, from teachers, school principals, to the minister of education will realize that there is extraordinary value contained in every subject, especially in this case social studies. By knowing how to be good in society, such as appreciating, respecting each other, and being aware of diversity, we will grow into a nation that is not only social but also good and capable in society.

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